

The American University in Cairo
Core Curriculum
SEMR 412/4038

South-South Dialogue: Perceptions and Reflections from the Global South

UW 2.00-3:15
Spring 2014

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Course Description

This videoconference dialogue course aims at offering a comparative view of and a fresh perspective on the ‘Global South’. The course shall use an interdisciplinary approach to explore the social, economic, political and cultural contexts of some of the countries/regions that constitute what is known today as the ‘Global South’ in an attempt to outline the commonalities as well as the differences that exist within this global conglomerate of nation-states. In this light, AUC will be holding videoconferences with various partner-universities and institutions in order for the class to share perspectives and first-hand experiences relating to the themes and topics of discussion with the partners. Specific readings will be assigned by AUC and the partnering universities to have a general introduction to the countries that will be studied and a specific background on the linkage these countries/geographical areas have with the Global South as an economic and a political amalgam. This is an interdisciplinary course that can be relevant to students from different backgrounds and disciplines, especially those that have an interest in contemporary development issues.

Aims and Objectives of the Course

The course aims to bring together students from the Global South alongside counterparts from AUC in order to explore a diverse set of issues pertaining to the social, economic and political contexts of a wide variety of developing countries. In doing so, it addresses selected current and possible future development issues from a regional as well as a global perspective.

Learning/Teaching methods

There will be two sessions held every week: a regular in-class session where the students meet to discuss the readings with the guidance of the lecturer, and a dialogue session where the two classes (from two different places) meet via video-conference and a joint session is held, co-facilitated by the lecturers from both sides. Students shall be given indicative readings on the topics and encouraged to explore them more widely and classroom activities will be augmented with guest speakers from different backgrounds and affiliations, whenever applicable. Specific topics and particular cases will be investigated further in discussions initiated (under guidance) by students. Given the nature of the subject matter, the resources utilized will not be confined to academic/scholarly books or articles, and sources of information such as blog posts, YouTube videos and Internet discussion forums will constitute a main part of the resources used. Whenever applicable, additional media resources, including feature films and documentaries, will also be utilized to enhance the exposure of the students to some of the everyday realities of the Global South. Class attendance and active verbal participation in class discussions and videoconference sessions are crucial elements of the work and it is expected of all students to engage in that process. In particular, students are expected to contribute with critical discussions of the reading assignments and thoughtful consideration of peer comments, and with discussion and critique of ideas and arguments presented, including those of the lecturer.

Assessment Overview

-Attendance & Participation.....	25%
-Presentation.....	15%
-Reaction Papers.....	40%
(Students are required to submit eight 1 to 2-page reaction papers on eight different weeks' readings)	
-Final Essay Paper.....	20%
(2000-3000 words, due final week. Essay question will be given to students at the end of the semester)	

Assessment Tasks

Attendance and Participation:

Active attendance and informed participation in class and videoconference sessions are of utmost importance in the context of this course. Not only will this enhance your chances of getting a better grade, but it will also strengthen your understanding of the subject matter. Please note that this mode of participation is only possible if you come to class prepared and do the assigned readings beforehand. You should feel entirely free to approach the lecturer anytime with any queries or comments you might have. You are also expected to make up for any missed work during your absence. Note that the participation grade will depend on both the quality and the quantity of student's comments and questions. Students are also strongly encouraged to constantly check their Blackboard in case of class time changes, announcements...etc.

Presentation:

All students are expected to give a 10 to 15-minute presentation on the theme/week of their choice. In your presentation please avoid the temptation to summarize the readings. Instead, pick one or two interesting and controversial points that the readings raise, discuss them critically, taking into account opposing perspectives, and in an organized manner. Your presentation should open the floor for a 5-minute class discussion moderated by you.

Reaction papers:

Students are expected to submit eight 1 to 2-page reaction papers that deal with issues raised in the weekly readings. The reaction paper may link different readings, point out their opposing perspectives, question key assumptions and hypotheses, or discuss an issue raised from various perspectives. Reaction papers should be submitted before Sunday class session. They account for 40% of the grade (5% each).

Final Essay Paper:

An essay question will be given to students around the end of the semester. The essay paper must be at least 2,000 and at most 3,000 words and accounts for 20% of the total grade.

Note on Academic Integrity

The discovery of any instance of plagiarism will lead to the filing of a report on the incident to the Academic Integrity Committee, as mandated by university policy. If you are uncertain about the definition of plagiarism, please ask the instructor before submitting work for this course.

SYLLABUS PLAN AND WEEKLY READINGS

Week 1 (Feb 2-5)

Introduction

Romney, Patricia "The Art of Dialogue," Animating Democracy:
http://www.romneyassociates.com/files/Art_of_dialogue.pdf

Week 2 (Feb 9-12)

Theme: What is the global South?

- Dirlik, Arif, "Global south: predicament and promise", The Global South, Volume 1, Numbers 1 & 2, 2007

- Berger, Mark T. "The end of the "Third World"?" Third World Quarterly, Vol. 15, No.2, June 1994:

<http://www.artsrn.ualberta.ca/courses/PoliticalScience/357B1/documents/MarkBergerTheEndOfTheThirdWorld.pdf>

Week 3 (Feb 16-19)/ with University of Western Cape (UWC), South Africa

Theme: Civil-military relations in Egypt and South Africa

- Perlmutter, Amos "The Praetorian state and the praetorian army: Toward a taxonomy of civil-military relations in developing polities," Comparative Politics, Vol. 1, No.3, April 1969

- Griffiths, Robert J., "South African civil-military relations in transition: Issues and influences," Armed forces & Society, Vol. 21, No. 3, Spring 1995

- Griffiths, Robert J., "Democratization and civil military relations in Namibia, South Africa and Mozambique," Third World Quarterly, Vol. 17, Issue 3, 1996

- Ngculu, James, "Civil-military relations and defence transformation in South Africa," In Williams, Rocky et al. (ed.), Ourselves to Know, ISSAfrica September 2002:

<http://www.issafrica.org/pubs/Books/OurselvesToKnow/Ngculu.pdf>

- Williams, Rocky, "Defense in a democracy: The South African defence review and the redefinitions of the parameters of the national defence debate" Ourselves to Know, ISSAfrica, September 2002

- Sayegh, Yezid, "Above the state: The officers' republic in Egypt," Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, August 2012:

http://carnegieendowment.org/files/officers_republic1.pdf

- Blog post: "Military tutelage Egyptian style":

http://baheyya.blogspot.com/2013/07/military-tutelage-egyptian-style_16.html

- Blogpost: "The future of civilian-military relations in Egypt":

<http://arabist.net/blog/2012/1/11/the-future-of-civilian-military-relations-in-egypt.html>

- Kazamias, Alexander, panel paper on "The Contradictions of Egypt's Post-revolutionary Experiment":

<http://podcasts.ox.ac.uk/panel-4-old-state-new-rules-praetorian-parliamentarism-contradictions-egypts-post>

Week 4 (Feb 23-26) Documentary: Darwin's Nightmare

Globalization and neoliberal development

- Mitchell, Timothy, "America's Egypt: Discourse of the development industry," MERIP, Vol. 21, 1991:

<http://www.merip.org/mer/mer169/americas-egypt>

- Bello, Walden, "Globalization in retreat: Capitalist overstretch, civil society and the crisis of the globalist project," Berkley Journal of Sociology, Vol. 51, 2007
- Dahlstrom, Lars, "The neoliberal smokescreen of poverty reduction in times of uncertainties, a 'newspeak' agenda?" Global South Network, July 2012:
<http://globalsouthnetwork.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/03/5.-The-smokescreen-of-poverty-reduction.docx>
- Armbrust, Walter "Egypt: A revolution against neoliberalism?" AlJazeera English, Opinion, February 2011:
<http://www.aljazeera.com/indepth/opinion/2011/02/201122414315249621.html>
- Mackell, Austin, "The IMF versus the Arab spring" The Guardian, May 2011:
<http://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2011/may/25/imf-arab-spring-loans-egypt-tunisia>

Week 5 (March 2-5) with Udayana University, Indonesia

Theme: The Military in Business

- "Too high a price" a Human Rights Watch report:
<http://www.hrw.org/sites/default/files/reports/indonesia0606.pdf>
- "Unkept promise" a Human Rights Watch report:
<http://www.hrw.org/sites/default/files/reports/indonesia0110webwcover.pdf>
- Abul-Magd, Zeinab, "The army and the economy in Egypt," Jadaliyya, Dec 23 2011:
<http://www.jadaliyya.com/pages/index/3732/the-army-and-the-economy-in-egypt>
- Marshall, Shana and Joshua Stacher, "Egypt's generals and transnational capital," MERIP, Vol. 42, Spring 2012 :
<http://www.merip.org/mer/mer262/egypts-generals-transnational-capital>
- Dorsey, James M., "Reform of Middle Eastern Militaries: Lessons from Indonesia", Huffington Post, May 2013:
http://www.huffingtonpost.com/james-dorsey/reform-of-middle-eastern-_b_3270508.html

Week 6 (Mar 9-12)

The "Arab Spring": what prospects for grassroots change in the South?

- Amar, Paul, "Mubarak's phantom presidency" AlJazeera English, Opinion, February 2011:
<http://www.aljazeera.com/indepth/opinion/2011/02/20112310511432916.html>
- Ottaway, Marina "Egypt's Democracy: Between the Military, Islamists and Illiberal Democrats," Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, November 2011:
<http://carnegieendowment.org/2011/11/03/egypt-s-democracy-between-military-islamists-and-illiberal-democrats/6mls#>
- Ottaway, Marina and Amr Hamzawy: "Protest Movements and Political Change in the Arab World," Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, January 28, 2011 :
http://carnegieendowment.org/files/OttawayHamzawy_Outlook_Jan11_ProtestMovements.pdf
- Boagaert, Koenraad, "Global dimensions of the Arab Spring and the potential for anti-hegemonic policies" Jadaliyya, December 2011:
<http://www.jadaliyya.com/pages/index/3638/global-dimensions-of-the-arab-spring-and-the-poten>
- Sallam, Hesham "Letting go of revolutionary purity" January 2014:
<http://www.jadaliyya.com/pages/index/16167/letting-go-of-revolutionary-purity>
- Kazamias, Alexander, panel paper on "The Contradictions of Egypt's Post-revolutionary Experiment":
<http://podcasts.ox.ac.uk/panel-4-old-state-new-rules-praetorian-parliamentarism-contradictions-egypts-post>

Week 7 (March 16-19) with Udayana University, Indonesia

Religious politics and democracy in the global South

- Beinin, Joel, "Political Islam and the New Global Economy: The Political Economy of an Egyptian Social Movement," *The New Centennial Review*, Volume 5, Number 1, Spring 2005
- Elsherif, Ashraf, "Egypt's post-Mubarak predicament," *Carnegie Endowment for International Peace*, January 2014:
http://carnegieendowment.org/files/post_mubarak_predicament.pdf
- Ottaway, Marina, "Egypt's Democracy - Between The Military, Islamists And Illiberal Democrats," *Midan Masr*, November 2011:
<http://www.midanmasr.com/en/article.aspx?ArticleID=145>
- Elsherif, Ashraf, "What path will Egypt Muslim Brotherhood choose," *Carnegie Endowment for International Peace*, September 23, 2013:
<http://carnegieendowment.org/2013/09/23/what-path-will-egypt-s-muslim-brotherhood-choose/gnx6>
- BBC Radio Analysis, "The Muslim Brotherhood: Why did they fail?":
<http://www.bbc.co.uk/programmes/b03bqfvv>
- Pranowo, Bambang, "Islam & Democracy: Experience of Indonesia", Paper presented at the Workshop on Islam, the State and Politics, Institute for Peace and Democracy, Serpong, April 2012
- Effendy, Bahtiar, "Islam & the State in the Indonesian Experience", Paper presented at the Workshop on Islam, the State and Politics, Institute for Peace and Democracy, Serpong, April 2012

Week 8 (March 23-26) with University of Western Cape (UWC), South Africa

Theme: How Constitutional law may consolidate political transformation

- Chaskalson, Arthur, "Dignity and justice for all", *Maryland Journal of International Law*, vol. 24, 2009
- and Peter E. Quint's response in the same issue: "The Universal Declaration [of Human Rights] and South African constitutional law: A response to justice Arthur Chaskalson"
- Africa Justice Foundation, "What can Egypt's Constitutional Court learn from South Africa?" August 2012:
<http://africajusticefoundation.org/our-blog/news-articles/what-can-egypts-constitutional-court-learn-from-south-africa/>
- Mallat, Chibli, "Saving Egypt's Supreme Constitutional Court from itself," June 2012:
<http://english.ahram.org.eg/NewsContentP/4/45009/Opinion/Saving-Egypt%E2%80%99s-Supreme-Constitutional-Court-from-i.aspx>
- Charbel, Jano, "An analysis of the draft constitution," January 2014 :
<http://madamasr.com/content/analysis-draft-constitution>
- Nasrawi, Salah, "A Revolutionary Constitution? Not Exactly" January 2014
<http://weekly.ahram.org.eg/News/5291/21/A-revolutionary-constitution--Not-exactly.aspx>
- Ali, Randa, "Inside Egypt's draft constitution: questions over social justice" December 2013:
<http://english.ahram.org.eg/NewsContent/1/64/88630/Egypt/Politics--/Inside-Egypt-s-draft-constitution-Questions-over-s.aspx>
- Gad, Sawsan, "Egypt's parallel constitution" October 2013:
<http://www.madamasr.com/content/egypt-parallel-constitution>
- Brown, Nathan and Michele Dunne, "Egypt's draft constitution rewards the military and judiciary," December 2013:
<http://egyptelections.carnegieendowment.org/2013/12/05/egypt%E2%80%99s-draft-constitution-rewards-the-military-and-judiciary>

Week 9 (March 30- April 2) with the American University of Nigeria

Theme: Security over democracy and human rights? Security sector corruption and state recourse to extrajudicial violence in the face of crime and terrorism in Egypt and Nigeria

- IRIN report:
<http://www.irinnews.org/report/95314/nigeria-urgent-need-for-police-reform>
- NPF portal announcing reformation:
<http://www.npf.gov.ng/news/reformation-agenda>
- Jonathan's statements June 13, 2013:
<http://www.thisdaylive.com/articles/jonathan-nigerians-don-t-have-confidence-in-police-but-rates-t-hem-high/150271/>
- Rogers, Paul, "Nigeria, the Boko Haram risk", Open Democracy, May 9, 2013:
<http://www.opendemocracy.net/paul-rogers/nigeria-boko-haram-risk>
- Akor, Christopher, "Longing for a strong man in Nigeria?" Democracy in Africa, October 3, 2013:
<http://democracyinafrica.org/longing-for-a-strongman-in-nigeria/>

- Fadel, Mohammad, "From democrats to terrorists," Boston Review Blog, January 8, 2014:
<http://www.bostonreview.net/blog/mohammad-fadel-muslim-brotherhood-terrorist-group-egypt>
- BBC news:
<http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/magazine-24477507>
- Egyptian Initiative for Personal Rights press release, January 2012:
<http://eipr.org/en/pressrelease/2012/01/04/1338>
- Fahmy, Khaled, "What doesn't Morsi understand about Police reform?" AlAhram Online, March 1, 2013:
<http://english.ahram.org.eg/NewsContentP/4/65849/Opinion/Egypt-What-doesnt-Morsi-understand-about-police-re.aspx>
- Rashed, Dina "Reforming the Egyptian Police?", Foreign Policy, July 8 2013:
http://mideastafrica.foreignpolicy.com/posts/2013/07/08/reforming_the_egyptian_police
- Carr, Sarah, "The popular war on terror," Mada Masr, July 25, 2013:
<http://www.jadaliyya.com/pages/index/13192/the-popular-war-on-terror->
- "Massacre in Cairo" Democracy Now, August 15, 2013:
http://www.democracynow.org/2013/8/15/massacre_in_cairo_egypt_on_brink
- Abu-Rish, Ziad "From Revolution to War on Terror," Jadaliyya, August 21, 2013:
http://www.jadaliyya.com/pages/index/13737/from-revolution-to-war-on-terror_reflections-on-po
- Egyptian Initiative for Personal Rights press release, November 2013:
<http://eipr.org/en/pressrelease/2013/11/07/1865>
- Yehia, Dina "Egypt's Anti-Terrorism Legislation" Mada Masr, November 2013:
<http://madamasr.com/content/egypt%E2%80%99s-anti-terrorism-legislation>
- DW news, "Police brutality in Egypt back in spotlight" December 18, 2013:
<http://www.dw.de/police-brutality-in-egypt-back-in-the-spotlight/a-17302014>
- Kenner, David "Egypt to Media: Don't you dare distort our war on terror" Foreign Policy, August 2013:
http://blog.foreignpolicy.com/posts/2013/08/18/egypt_to_foreign_journalists_shape_up

Week 10 (April 6-9) with the American University of Nigeria

Sectarianism in the global South: roots and solutions? the experiences of Egypt and Nigeria

- Stambolyiska, Ranya, "Sectarian violence sweeps over Egypt" August 2013:
<http://www.jadaliyya.com/pages/index/13660/sectarian-violence-sweeps-over-egypt->
- Hellyer, H. A., "The Scourge of sectarianism in Egypt", June 2013:
http://mideastafrica.foreignpolicy.com/posts/2013/06/26/the_scourge_of_sectarianism_in_egypt
- Goldberg, Ellis, "Two Saints and a Sinner", April 2013:
<http://www.jadaliyya.com/pages/index/11077/two-saints-and-a-sinner>
- "Human Rights Watch report on sectarian violence in Egypt" July 2012:
<http://english.ahram.org.eg/NewsContent/1/64/47838/Egypt/Politics-/HRW-full-text-of-report-on-se>

[ctarian-violence-in-E.aspx](#)

- HRW “Egypt: Sectarian Attacks amidst political crisis” July 2013

<http://www.hrw.org/news/2013/07/23/egypt-sectarian-attacks-amid-political-crisis>

- EIPR report: “Two Years of Sectarian Violence: What happened? Where do we begin? An Analytical Study of Jan 2008 -Jan 2010,” April 2010. Particularly the following sections:

* How does the state address sectarian violence?

<http://eipr.org/en/report/2010/04/11/776/785>

<http://eipr.org/en/report/2010/04/11/776/786>

<http://eipr.org/en/report/2010/04/11/776/787>

* Where does the solution begin:

<http://eipr.org/en/report/2010/04/11/776/788>

- “Nigeria set for sectarian violence”, January 2012:

<http://thinkafricapress.com/nigeria/set-sectarian-violence>

- Markoe, Lawrence, “Nigeria: five things to know about religious violence”, July 2012:

http://www.huffingtonpost.com/2012/07/14/nigeria-religious-violence_n_1672693.html

- Brock, Joe, “Nigeria largely ignores sectarian violence: Human Rights Watch”, December 2013:

<http://www.reuters.com/article/2013/12/12/us-nigeria-violence-idUSBRE9BB0BL20131212>

Week 11 (Spring Break)

Week 12 (April 23)

Managing urban space in the global South, Comparing Brazil and Egypt

- Fernandes, Edesio, “Implementing the Urban Reform Agenda in Brazil: Possibilities, Challenges, and Lessons” Urban Forum 22, 2011

- Harvey, David, “The Right to the City” International Journal of Urban and Regional Research 27:4, 2003

- Dorman, W Judson: The Politics of Neglect: The Egyptian State in Cairo, 1974-98. School of Oriental and African Studies, University of London, 2007, Introduction:

http://eprints.soas.ac.uk/155/1/Dorman_Politics_of_Neglect.pdf

- Naguib, Rime “Neoliberal Cairo: Whose city?” Egypt Independent, July 2010:

<http://www.egyptindependent.com//opinion/neoliberal-cairo-whose-city>

- Mitchell, Timothy, “Dreamland: The Neoliberalism of your desire,” MERIP Spring 1999:

<http://www.merip.org/mer/mer210/dreamland-neoliberalism-your-desires>

- “10 must-watch videos to understand Egypt's urban challenges” read the piece and watch the videos here:

<http://cities.jadaliyya.com/pages/index/15281/ten-must-watch-videos-to-understand-egypt%E2%80%99s-urban->

Week 13 (April 27-30)

Human development in the global South? The right to health care

- UNDP, Human Development Report 2013: The rise of the global south:

http://hdr.undp.org/sites/default/files/hdr2013_en_summary.pdf

- Third World Network, “Health crisis in developing countries”:

<http://www.twinside.org.sg/title/twr131a.htm>

- Hong, Evelyn, “Globalization and the Impact on Health”, August 2000

<http://www.twinside.org.sg/title/health.pdf>

- Reading, Joshua P., “Who's responsible for this? The globalization of healthcare in developing countries”, 2010

<http://www.repository.law.indiana.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1427&context=ijgls>

- Mosireen, “Egypt: The right to healthcare” (Video):
<http://creativetimereports.org/2012/09/24/election-report-the-right-to-healthcare/>
- Center for Economic and Social Rights, “Egypt: Factsheet No.13”:
<http://www.cesr.org/downloads/Egypt.Factsheet.web.pdf?preview=1>
- Iskander, Dina, “The right to health: a case study of Hepatitis C in Egypt” December 2013:
<https://dar.aucegypt.edu/bitstream/handle/10526/3748/Thesis%20IHRL%20-%20Dina%20Iskander%20Dec2013.pdf?sequence=3>
- Yehia, Hayat, “Egypt's Elusive Medicines” November 2013:
<http://weekly.ahram.org.eg/News/4726/32/Egypt%E2%80%99s-elusive-medicines.aspx>
- EIPR, “The TRIPS agreement and Egypt's responsibility to protect the right to health”, January 2005 (report divided in topics):
<http://www.eipr.org/en/report/2005/01/01/848>

Week 14 (May 4-7)

Violence against women in the global South, roots and solution

- Global gender gap report, 2013. Country profile: Egypt:
<http://reports.weforum.org/global-gender-gap-report-2013/>
- Moghadam, Valentine, “The Feminization of poverty and women human rights”:
http://www.cpahq.org/cpahq/cpadocs/Feminization_of_Poverty.pdf
- “Studies on ways and methods to eliminate sexual harassment in Egypt”,
http://www.dgvn.de/fileadmin/user_upload/DOKUMENTE/English_Documents/Sexual-Harassment-Study-Egypt-Final-EN.pdf
- Ilahi, Nadia “Gender Contestations: An analysis of street harassment in Cairo and its implications for women's access to public spaces”:
http://www.aucegypt.edu/gapp/igws/gradcent/documents/surfacing_vol2-no1_05ilahi.pdf
- Gamil, Deena, “Sexual Harassment in Egypt Linked to Wider Violence”:
<http://www.trust.org/item/20131111125919-dcup0>
- Young Urban Indians find political voice after student's gang rape:
<http://www.reuters.com/article/2013/01/01/us-india-rape-politics-idUSBRE90009M20130101>
- The Advocates for Human Rights “Causes of sexual harassment”:
<http://www1.umn.edu/humanrts/svaw/harassment/explore/3causes.htm>
- “How do we stop rape: India look for answers”
<http://www.tehelka.com/delhi-gangrape-outraged-india-reacts/>
- Bhalla, Nita, “ As India gang rape trial ends, a debate over what has changed”:
<http://www.trust.org/item/20130906170502-jexnb/?source=spotlight>

Week 15 (May 11-14)

Theme: the prospects of the global south: BRICS and others

- Puri, Hardeep S., “Rise of the global South and its impact on South-South Cooperation,” the World Bank Institute, 2010:
<http://siteresources.worldbank.org/WBI/Resources/213798-1286217829056/puri.pdf>
- Broadman, Harry G., “China and India go to Africa: New Deals in the Developing World,” Foreign Affairs, March/April 2008:
<http://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/63224/harry-g-broadman/china-and-india-go-to-africa>
- Gupta, Anil K. and Haiyan Wang, “Myths about China and India's Africa race”, Bloomberg Businessweek, October 2011:
www.businessweek.com/asia/myths-about-china-and-indias-africa-race-09222011.html
- Cho, Hee-Yeon, “Second death’, or revival of the ‘third world’ in the context of neo-liberal globalization,” Inter-Asia Cultural Studies, Vol. 6, No. 4, 2005:

<http://www.artsrn.ualberta.ca/courses/PoliticalScience/357B1/documents/ChoSecondDeathOrRevivalofThirdWorldNeolibGlobal.pdf>

- Thomas Jr., Landon “Fragile five is the latest club of emerging nations in turmoil” The New York Times, January 2014:

http://www.nytimes.com/2014/01/29/business/international/fragile-five-is-the-latest-club-of-emerging-nations-in-turmoil.html?_r=1